

Responsible Evaluation of AI for Mental Health

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Abstract

Although artificial intelligence (AI) shows growing promise for mental health care, current approaches to evaluating AI tools in this domain remain fragmented and poorly aligned with clinical practice, social context, and first-hand user experience. This paper argues for a rethinking of *responsible evaluation* – what is measured, by whom, and for what purpose – by introducing an interdisciplinary framework that integrates clinical soundness, social context, and equity, providing a structured basis for evaluation. Through an analysis of 135 recent *ACL publications, we identify recurring limitations, including over-reliance on generic metrics that do not capture clinical validity, therapeutic appropriateness, or user experience, limited participation from mental health professionals, and insufficient attention to safety and equity. To address these gaps, we propose a taxonomy of AI mental health support types – assessment-, intervention-, and information synthesis-oriented – each with distinct risks and evaluative requirements, and illustrate its use through case studies.

<https://ukplab.github.io/nlp-mh-evals/>

1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) hold considerable promise for advancing mental health research and practice. They offer new tools at scale to support diagnosis, therapy, peer-support, and self-guided support, where users interact with LLMs directly for guidance or coping strategies (Demszky et al., 2023; Cruz-Gonzalez et al., 2025). From detecting early signs of depression in language (Lan et al., 2025), to clinical documentation and summarizing complex patient histories (Shah et al., 2025; Srivastava et al., 2024), and generating therapeutic or supportive responses in online communities (Liu et al., 2021; Gabriel et al., 2024), AI-enabled mental health tools have the potential to augment pro-

fessional care and extend psychological support beyond traditional clinical encounters. This potential is especially valuable due to the limited availability of mental health resources, growing global demand, and persistent inequities in access to care ¹.

Despite their promise, AI mental health tools are fundamentally lacking in evaluation. Existing evaluation practices are inconsistent (Yang et al., 2021; Aich et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2024b) and often insufficient (Tornero-Costa et al., 2023). This is concerning because poor evaluation, particularly in this domain, can lead to misleading conclusions, unintended harm, and inequitable outcomes. Recurring issues include over-reliance on generic metrics that fail to capture clinical validity, therapeutic appropriateness, or user experience, minimal participation from mental health professionals, and insufficient attention to safety, equity, and long-term impact. While we do *not* expect papers in venues like ACL to be fully deployable in clinical settings, careful evaluation is essential to responsibly translate research insights toward real-world mental health impact. Our goal is to raise evaluation standards as much as possible so that research outputs can earn the trust and approval of domain experts, even when the tools are not yet – or are not intended to be – used in actual clinical practice.

These limitations are not idiosyncratic model bugs, but symptoms of an underlying disconnect between the communities that build, use, and regulate AI for mental health tools. Current evaluations often default to technical benchmark wins, while clinicians and other users judge success by changes in symptoms, patient functioning, and safety over time; social and implementation scientists, in turn, ask whether a tool fits workflows, earns trust, and reaches people equitably. Without a shared evaluative language, results travel poorly across these communities: automated scores with-

¹WHO 2025 report.

out clinical anchors may overstate progress, “human studies” may lack meaningful involvement as well as methodological transparency or expert input, and cross-disciplinary collaboration may arrive late – if at all. What is needed is a common, clinically grounded evaluation framework that makes psychometric constructs accessible to AI researchers, pairs them with human-centered and implementation-science measures, and treats safety, equity, and real-world utility as primary outcomes. This framework can then be the connective tissue that enables mutual intelligibility and, ultimately, responsible deployment across research contexts, clinics, and community platforms.

Consequently, we posit a fundamental reconsideration of evaluation for AI mental health tools according to clinical goals, typically falling into three broad types: **(1) assessment** for inferring psychological states (e.g., language-based screening), **(2) interventions** to deliver or scaffold support (e.g., therapeutic chatbots), and **(3) information synthesis** to aid practitioners or researchers (e.g., clinical summarization). This categorization clarifies how different types of tools require context-sensitive evaluation and enables the field to calibrate what claims are supported by existing evaluations.

Contributions. Our paper makes four primary contributions. (1) We identify key gaps and challenges in current evaluation practices for AI in mental health (§ 2; see Appendix A for details of surveyed papers); (2) we propose a structured taxonomy of tool types and salient evaluation dimensions, highlighting differences between general generative AI evaluation and mental health specific concerns (§ 3); (3) we demonstrate its utility through five illustrative case studies spanning assessment, intervention, and support tools in diverse settings (§ 4); and (4), we synthesize these insights into recommendations and guiding principles for responsible and comprehensive evaluation moving forward (§ 5).

Positionality. Our call for rethinking evaluation aligns with the broader reflection on the generative AI evaluation crisis in the *CL community (Bomasani, 2023; Elangovan et al., 2024; Kotonya and Toni, 2024; Zhou et al., 2025b), which emphasizes the limitations of relying solely on automated metrics and benchmarks. Recent surveys on LLMs in psychotherapy (Na et al., 2025), cognitive distortion detection (Sage et al., 2025), and mental health conversational agents (Atapattu et al., 2025) highlight tasks and models but less so *how tools should*

Observed practice	%
Rely <u>only</u> on AI/NLP metrics	50
<u>No</u> human evaluation	52
With human evaluation but <u>no</u> experts	29
Evaluation guidelines <u>not</u> shared	17
Limitations in evaluation <u>not</u> discussed	36

Table 1: Overview of the ACL Anthology study conducted to ground our position. We queried the ACL Anthology database with mental health keywords², restricting results to the past five years and papers of types “main” or “findings”. This yielded 135 papers on mental health³. These manually-made observations provide context for our broader discussion of challenges and gaps in the evaluation of AI tools for mental health. We show details about the surveyed papers in Appendix A; Tables 3–17.

be evaluated responsibly, i.e., in ways that account for clinical validity, user experience, ethical considerations, safety, and equitable outcomes. We extend this conversation by proposing an interdisciplinary framework emphasizing clinical soundness, social context, equity, and user experience as central to evaluation in mental health AI.

2 Observed Practices

To ground our position, we conducted a quantitative analysis of 135 papers on mental health, published in the ACL Anthology⁴ over the past 5 years, with 36% of them published in 2025. Table 1 summarizes key patterns that emerged from this review, and Appendix A provides detailed annotations, including the tasks covered by these papers, and the observed practices documented at a paper level. Overall, we found that current evaluation practices in this literature remain limited in scope and rigor, especially considering the sensitivity and clinical implications of the domain. While the surveyed works cover a wide range of tasks, from detecting mental health conditions (Chen et al., 2024b; Yang et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2024a) to building therapeutic chatbots (Saha et al., 2022; Deng et al., 2023; Shim, 2021), their evaluations often rely on narrow, model-centric criteria.

²mental health, mental disorder, mental illness, therapy and psychiatry; Either in the title or in the abstract.

³After manual inspection to remove papers that mention mental health *only in passing* but not as the main focus; We had 152 papers before the inspection.

⁴<https://aclanthology.org/>; query date: 11-2025.

Specifically, five concerning patterns emerge. Half of the papers rely *only* on standard AI/NLP metrics such as accuracy, F1, BLEU, or ROUGE, ignoring psychological validity or clinical relevance. Over half (54%) include *no* human evaluation, and among those that do, 29% do so *without* involving mental health experts. Nearly one-fifth of papers omit evaluation guidelines, and roughly a third fail to discuss limitations in the way the evaluations have been conducted. These gaps indicate that current practices assess technical performance but often overlook safety, interpretability, and real-world utility (Thieme et al., 2020).

Overall, these findings reveal a methodological gap: AI tools may score well on generic NLG metrics yet fall short of clinical standards or user needs. This critique is not aimed at individual works, but rather, highlights the need for shared, rigorous evaluation practices. The following sections build on these observations to introduce a taxonomy (§ 3), illustrate it with case studies (§ 4), and present guiding principles for a clinically grounded and human-centered evaluation (§ 5).

3 Proposed Taxonomy

While new principles are needed to evaluate AI for mental health, there is much to build on from a century of work in psychological assessment (*classical quantitative methods* (Cook and Beckman, 2006)) and recent advances in applying technology in human-computer interaction and health (*implementation science* (Lyon et al., 2023)).

Classical quantitative methods. *Validity* and *reliability* are foundational in psychological evaluation⁵. *Validity* asks whether a tool *does what it is intended to do*, while *reliability* asks *whether it does so consistently*. Most current evaluations in AI mental health work mainly focuses on one validity subtype, namely construct validity, for example, through agreement with human annotations or existing scales (Park et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2024a), but this is only a starting point for high-stakes applications. A classifier may correlate with overall depression severity yet fail to predict specific symptoms or generalize across populations. Similarly, a summarization tool may align with expert summaries but omit safety-critical information or misinterpret non-clinical expressions, thus highlighting limits in discriminant validity and generalization.

⁵Evidenced by their inclusion in nearly every modern textbook on psychological research methods (Cohen et al., 1988; Reynolds and Livingston, 2021; Meyer, 2010)

Near-perfect construct validity is not always desirable, as even established assessments have limitations.

Implementation science. Recent advances in health informatics and human-computer interaction highlight that barriers to using AI go beyond validity and reliability (Reddy, 2024). Implementation science adds two pillars: *implementation*—whether an AI tool is feasible, acceptable, fits workflows, and improves outcomes safely; and *maintenance*—whether it remains effective over time, handling population shifts, language drift, inequities, or unintended consequences. Together with validity and reliability, these four pillars define a multidimensional evaluation space for AI in mental health across assessment, interventions, and information synthesis (i.e., therapist support).

To organize these concepts, we introduce a taxonomy of evaluation dimensions (Table 2⁶), mapping classical psychometrics and implementation science principles onto three common AI applications: assessment, intervention, and information synthesis. These evaluation paradigms are multifaceted; no single score can capture the full opportunities and risks of AI, akin to a cockpit dashboard where multiple readings are needed to assess performance.

Assessments involve tools for measurement, screening, aiding diagnosis, or forecasting (e.g., scoring depression severity, estimating suicide risk from social media, classifying psychosis-related language). *Validity* focuses on convergent validity (alignment with other measures of the same construct), discriminant validity (avoiding spurious alignment with different constructs), and criterion validity (relation to meaningful external outcomes like hospitalization or symptom trajectories). *Reliability* covers stability over time (test-retest), robustness across populations (clinics, demographics, cultures, neurodivergent groups), and internal consistency (coherent subcomponents). *Implementation* examines feasibility, impact on diagnostic accuracy, equity, acceptability, and bias mitigation. *Maintenance* involves monitoring generalizability, performance drift, population-level outcomes, unintended consequences, and evolving language norms.

Interventions are tools aimed at changing outcomes, such as treatment agents, self-help aids, prevention nudges, or adaptive therapy recommen-

⁶While our focus is on clinical integration, this taxonomy is intended to also cover peer-supported and community-based AI mental health tools.

Support type	Quality Criteria		Real-World Use	
	Validity <i>Does it do what it is intended?</i>	Reliability <i>Does it do the same thing under different conditions?</i>	Implementation <i>Can it be used effectively in real-world contexts?</i>	Maintenance <i>Does it remain effective and appropriate over time as users and contexts evolve?</i>
Assessment (e.g., language-based screening)	<p>1. Construct Validity: How much does it match other tools or indicators (e.g., clinical, community, or self-report measures) intended to assess the same construct (convergent) or a different construct (discriminant)?</p> <p>2. Criterion Validity: What is its association with external, theoretically-related constructs or outcomes (e.g., wellbeing, functioning, participation)?</p>	<p>1. Across Time: What is the test-retest stability (at appropriate time intervals)? Does it [not] change if it should [not]?</p> <p>2. Across Populations: Does it work just as well across different cultures, locations, neurodivergent populations?</p> <p>3. Internal Consistency: To what extent do all components or interactions of the tool function consistently?</p>	<p>1. Feasibility: Does it fit into the workflows and routines of intended users (e.g., clinicians, peer supporters, or individuals)?</p> <p>2. Effectiveness and Usefulness (extrinsic): Is it consistent across diverse populations? Does it improve diagnostic accuracy in practice?</p> <p>3. Acceptability: Are data gathering and feedback mechanisms for assessment acceptable to both patients and clinicians?</p>	<p>1. Generalizability and Impact: Does performance remain stable as users or contexts evolve over time? Does it contribute to improved individual or population-level outcomes?</p> <p>2. Unintended Consequences: Is it creating labeling bias?</p>
Intervention (e.g., therapeutic chatbots)	<p>1. Construct Validity: Does it make a change in the intended direction (convergent) or have any adverse or unintended effects (discriminant)? From experimentation, RCTs, or real-world trials (efficacy or effectiveness).</p> <p>2. Criterion Validity: Does it predict or improve external downstream outcomes (e.g., wellbeing, functioning, relationships, work, community participation)?</p>	<p>1. Across Time: Does it keep working as well at future points in time?</p> <p>2. Across Populations: Is the effect the same across cultures, locations, neurodivergence?</p> <p>3. Internal consistency: If the intervention has multiple mechanisms or components, do they each contribute consistently to desired outcomes?</p>	<p>1. Effectiveness: Does it improve symptoms, wellbeing, or functioning under real-world conditions (with or without clinician involvement)?</p> <p>2. Usability and Engagement: Do users adhere to the intervention? Is it easy to use?</p> <p>3. Implementation Risk: Is it being used as intended?</p> <p>4. Equity and Acceptability: Do diverse user groups find it acceptable and trustworthy? Are potential biases mitigated?</p>	<p>1. Stability: Does the benefit sustain over time across different user groups and contexts? Are there equitable outcomes and access?</p> <p>2. Safety: Are there emergent risks or harmful use patterns?</p>
Information synthesis (e.g., clinical summarization)	<p>1. Construct Validity: Does it provide accurate, contextually appropriate, and unbiased summaries or recommendations?</p> <p>2. Criterion Validity: Does it save users (e.g., clinicians or peer supporters) time or improve the quality of their decisions?</p>	<p>1. Scenarios: Does it perform reliably across different use scenarios?</p> <p>2. Services: Does it integrate effectively across different service models or modalities?</p>	<p>1. Acceptability: Would intended users (clinicians, patients, peer supporters, community workers) accept and trust the tool in their workflows or daily lives?</p> <p>2. Usefulness: Do the users find it useful in their everyday work or well-being activities?</p> <p>3. Impact: Does the support improve outcomes for users or beneficiaries (e.g., efficiency, understanding, well-being)?</p> <p>4. Equity and Bias Mitigation: Are there systematic biases in recommendations or summaries? Are they identified and mitigated?</p>	<p>1. Tool-level Impact: Does it reduce administrative load, emotional burden, or improve care and support quality across settings?</p> <p>2. Unintended Consequences: Does it foster over-reliance or skill atrophy?</p>

Table 2: Taxonomy for evaluation of AI in mental health applications: aligning support types with validity, reliability, implementation, and maintenance across various contexts.

dations. Validity includes construct validity (delivering the intended therapeutic ingredient), efficacy (producing beneficial change and avoiding harm), and criterion validity (predicting improvements in functioning, relationships, or job stability). Reliability examines whether effects hold across time, populations, settings, and intervention components. Implementation considers real-world symptom improvement, user engagement, clinician usability, low risk, and monitoring off-label use. Maintenance evaluates persistence of benefits and emergence of new risks, such as overuse or avoidance of human care.

Information synthesis tools augment care and administration efficiently. For automated care aids (clinical summarization, triage notes, treatment recommendations), convergent validity asks whether outputs are accurate as per the clinical evidence base, while criterion validity asks whether they save clinician time or improve documentation. Reliability emphasizes reproducibility across scenarios (note types, specialties) and modalities (telehealth vs. in-person, EHR variants). Implementation focuses on acceptability, usefulness in daily work, and patient impact. Maintenance considers tool-level effects, like reduced burnout or unintended consequences (over-reliance, skill atrophy).

In our evaluation framework, we prioritize these evaluation dimensions because they draw from long-standing clinical science (validity and reliability) and real-world mental health technology evaluation (implementation and maintenance), together defining the minimum requirements for responsible use in high-stakes mental health contexts.

4 Case Studies

The following five case studies were selected to illustrate the taxonomy across support types. They were chosen for their representativeness, methodological rigor, and the variety of AI approaches they exemplify, enabling a comprehensive demonstration of the taxonomy’s dimensions: *validity*, *reliability*, *implementation*, and *maintenance*.

4.1 Study I (Assessment): LLM rating scales for psychometric assessment of patient engagement

Eberhardt et al. (2025) introduced the LLM rating scale, a psychometric tool for automatically transcribed psychotherapy sessions that measures latent psychological constructs, such as patient en-

gagement, by applying traditional psychometric principles to AI-based assessment. The scale uses structured items—prompts like “Please rate how motivated the patient is to engage in therapy on a scale from 0 to 100”—to elicit zero-shot judgments from the model. The study analyzed 1,131 sessions from 155 patients using the DISCOVER framework (Hallmen et al., 2025), computing mean scale scores from a large pool of manually developed items, which were then evaluated for reliability and multiple forms of validity.

Validity was assessed across multiple dimensions. Construct validity was supported by moderate, significant correlations between LLM rating scale scores and engagement determinants like therapy motivation and between-session effort (Holdsworth et al., 2014). Criterion validity was shown through associations with subsequent therapy outcomes, where higher engagement predicted greater symptom improvement. Structural validity was evaluated via multilevel confirmatory factor analysis modeling a single latent factor, with good fit (CFI = 0.968, SRMR = 0.022) though RMSEA = 0.108 indicated some unexplained variance. Reliability was examined as the consistency of the measurement across items, with internal consistency (McDonald’s ω = 0.953) showing coherent and stable LLM responses.

The study demonstrated the psychometric soundness and potential of the LLM rating scale as an automated tool for psychotherapy research and feedback. Future work should extend analyses across time and populations, assess robustness, fairness, and safety (Lutz et al., 2024; Ryan et al., 2025), and validate across contexts, languages, and constructs. Implementation considerations, including presentation and integration (e.g., via XAI (Lavelle-Hill et al., 2025)), affect real-world usefulness. Testing within systems like the Trier Treatment Navigator (Lutz et al., 2024, 2025) can evaluate clinical integration and early detection potential. Ongoing maintenance is needed to monitor drift, bias, and improvements with newer LLMs.

4.2 Study II (Assessment): Natural language response formats for assessing depression and worry

Gu et al. (2025) conducted a validity- and reliability-based comparison of response formats for LLM-based assessment of depression and worry, building on prior work showing AI language assessments can approach the reliability of human

scales (Kjell et al., 2022). The study compared four response formats, from closed to open (predefined words, descriptive words, short phrases, full-text responses), using a Sequential Evaluation with Model Pre-Registration (SEMP) design. Models were trained on a development set ($N = 963$) and pre-registered before evaluation on a prospective test set ($N = 145$) with validated scales, including the PHQ-9 (Spitzer et al., 1999) and GAD-7 (Spitzer et al., 2006). The results showed strong convergent validity across formats, with correlations of $r = .60-.79$, exceeding the pre-registered threshold ($r > .50$). Combining all eight depression and worry models yielded correlations near or above scale reliability limits (e.g., $r = .83$ for CES-D vs. reliability $r = .78$), and incremental validity analyses showed improved accuracy consistent with cognitive interview theory. However, high inter-correlations among combined models ($r = .88-.95$) indicated reduced discriminant validity when the same responses were used to assess both constructs.

Regarding reliability and implementation, two-week test-retest correlations showed moderate to strong stability, with performance generalizing well to unseen data and prospective accuracies matching cross-validated estimates. Open-ended formats showed internal consistency at the word level, with depression- (e.g., “blue”) and worry-related (e.g., “anxious”) terms aligning with DSM-5 symptom clusters (Diagnostic, 2013). Implementation effectiveness was demonstrated by predicting behavioral indicators such as sick leave and mental health-related healthcare visits, often matching or exceeding standard rating scales. Feasibility analyses showed that open formats provided richer information (Shannon diversity up to 561.0) but required longer completion times (up to 4 times slower than select-word tasks).

Overall, within the proposed taxonomy, this work shows strong convergent, criterion, and external validity and temporal reliability, indicating that well-designed LLM-based assessments can rival traditional measures. However, discriminant validity and workflow feasibility remain open questions, motivating future work on cross-population reliability and integration into digital clinical platforms.

4.3 Study III (*Intervention*): Evaluating the capabilities of LLMs vs. human therapists to generate personalized interventions

Bar-Shachar et al. (2025) developed an LLM-based

tool for generating context-sensitive therapeutic interventions during psychotherapy sessions. It uses four specialized LLM agents, supportive, directive, exploratory, and meaning-making, along with a Judge-LLM that selects the most appropriate intervention based on the dialogue and the patient’s emotional and cognitive state. This setup reflects how clinicians choose among multiple interventions and tailor responses to patients’ evolving needs.

They evaluated the tool via human-AI comparisons on transcribed therapy segments, with both therapists and the AI generating interventions that expert clinicians rated for theoretical appropriateness, contextual fit, and helpfulness. High inter-rater reliability (ICC and Cohen’s κ) supported robustness, and AI interventions were generally clinically relevant and sometimes approached human quality, though they lacked the depth and personalization of experienced clinicians.

Applying the taxonomy shows strong construct validity and reliability, supported by theoretical grounding and high rater agreement. However, ecological validity across therapies, languages, and contexts, fairness across groups, and key implementation and maintenance issues, such as feasibility, clinician acceptance, ethical oversight, model stability, and unintended effects, were not addressed.

Using the taxonomy, future evaluations could go beyond expert ratings by testing validity across modalities, populations, and contexts, examining reliability across models and raters, and focusing on implementation through usability, clinician-patient co-creation, and ethical integration. Ongoing maintenance would monitor drift, bias, and unintended effects, including impacts on novice therapists, ensuring the tool remains theoretically sound, reliable, and clinically sustainable.

4.4 Study IV (*Intervention*): A clinically-grounded framework for evaluating LM-assisted cognitive restructuring

Sharma et al. (2023, 2024) conducted a multi-stage project to design, deploy, as well as evaluate a human-LM interaction tool for cognitive restructuring, a core Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) technique. Across all stages, the project integrated clinical validity, ecological evaluation, safety, and equity considerations.

The first stage defined and validated clinically meaningful AI objectives. Working with mental health professionals, the authors developed 7 lin-

guistic attributes for reframing, including empathy, positivity, actionability, specificity, and addressing thinking traps. To ensure clinical validity, 600 reframes were collected and annotated by practitioners. A randomized field study ($N = 2,067$) on the Mental Health America platform showed users preferred highly empathic and specific reframes, while overly positive ones were less effective.

Under the implementation dimension, the framework was operationalized into an interactive LM-powered tool supporting users in cognitive restructuring. Co-designed with mental health professionals, it included safety mechanisms such as classification and rule-based filtering, IRB approval, and a user-reporting function, with flagged content (0.65%) confirming filter effectiveness. A large-scale field study on the MHA website ($N = 15,531$) evaluated user-reported outcomes, including emotional impact, therapeutic utility, and skill acquisition. The tool showed measurable benefits, with the majority of participants reporting reduced negative emotion and helpfulness of reframes for overcoming negative thoughts.

Under maintenance, the third stage assessed equity and found reduced effectiveness for adolescents aged 13-17. Targeted adaptations (simpler, more casual reframes) improved helpfulness in a follow-up trial without affecting other groups, demonstrating ongoing monitoring and refinement.

This case study shows how a clinically grounded, real-world evaluation framework centered on safety and equity can produce a tool with measurable utility. From a taxonomy perspective, it shows validity (clinically aligned outcomes), reliability (consistent effects), safety (content filtering and user flagging), equity (targeted improvements), and maintenance (iterative refinement). The tool has since been deployed by Mental Health America, serving over 160,000 users ⁷.

4.5 Study V (*Information synthesis*): Hierarchical LLM-VAE tool for clinically meaningful timeline summarization

Song et al. (2024) proposed a hybrid tool that integrates hierarchical variational autoencoders (TH-VAEs) with LLMs to generate clinically meaningful summaries of long-term social media timelines. It produces two layers: a first-person evidence summary capturing subjective experiences, and a

third-person clinical summary mapping these experiences to diagnostic indicators, interpersonal patterns, and moments of change. The goal is to help clinicians and researchers synthesize key information from longitudinal mental health data.

Evaluation of the tool integrated both automatic and expert-based components. Automatic metrics assessed meaning preservation, factual consistency, evidence appropriateness, coherence, and fluency. Clinical experts rated summaries for usefulness, diagnostic accuracy, and their ability to reflect dynamic psychological processes. Inter-rater agreement ensured the reliability of human judgments, and ablation studies tested the contribution of specific model components, such as keyphrase extraction and expert-informed prompting.

Applying the proposed taxonomy shows that the work addresses construct validity—alignment with clinical constructs—and criterion validity through correlations with expert judgments. It also touches on reliability via inter-rater agreement. However, because the tool was trained and evaluated only on social media data, ecological validity and clinical generalizability is limited. Although the peer-support platform provides authentic language, selective self-disclosure gives the model only a partial view of users' psychological states. The authors also acknowledge risks such as hallucinations, bias, and unsafe inferences, but do not systematically evaluate them, nor do they assess fairness across demographic or linguistic groups. Implementation and maintenance factors—such as clinical usability, practitioner acceptance, and long-term model stability—were likewise not examined.

Future work could extend evaluation to generalizability, usability, and sustainability. Ecological testing across cultures and clinical contexts, repeated assessments for reliability, clinician-focused implementation studies, and ongoing monitoring for drift or bias would support consistent performance, advancing the tool from proof of concept to a clinically robust, ethical, and sustainable mental health tool.

5 Moving Forward

Evaluation foundations and maturity pathways. Evaluation practices in AI for mental health remain concentrated in early-stage technical validation, with relatively few tools reaching implementation or maintenance. While this is typical for an emerging field, it motivates the need for ex-

⁷<https://screening.mhanational.org/changing-thoughts-with-an-ai-assistant/>

explicit *minimum evaluation standards* appropriate for high-risk mental health contexts. Assessment tools should demonstrate convergent and discriminant validity with clinical constructs. Intervention tools should provide evidence of therapeutic benefit, safety, and acceptability, ideally supported by prospective or randomized evaluations (Hofmann and Weinberger, 2013; Cuijpers et al., 2019). Information synthesis tools should document measurable improvements in workflow, decision quality, or clinical comprehension.

A robust evaluation strategy requires a multilayered, standardized pipeline, in which evaluation depth increases with a tool’s intended role and potential harm. We distinguish three maturity layers:

1. **Early maturity (exploratory):** Technical validation, including accuracy, robustness, and agreement with human annotations, typically using retrospective datasets. At this stage, evaluation supports feasibility assessment and hypothesis generation rather than clinical claims.
2. **Intermediate maturity (validation):** Human-centered evaluation, capturing expert judgment, usability, acceptability, and perceived clinical relevance, often through prospective or external validation and structured user studies.
3. **Advanced maturity (deployment):** Assessment of contextual and ecological characteristics, including workflow integration, feasibility across settings, long-term impact, equity, safety, and monitoring of failure modes over time.

This layered structure is particularly important in mental health settings, where concerns about invasiveness, reduced human oversight, and potential clinician deskilling are longstanding (Torous et al., 2019).

Safety, fairness, and adaptability. Safety and fairness require proactive, domain-specific protocols rather than retrospective checks. Because mental health involves power asymmetries and heightened risks of harm, AI support must be systematically stress-tested for hallucinations, inappropriate reassurance, and biased outputs. Fairness assessments should examine performance across demographic, cultural, and linguistic groups, acknowledging that fairness definitions entail unavoidable

trade-offs (Kleinberg et al., 2016; Ryan et al., 2025). Notable, most of our case studies lacked explicit safety or fairness evaluations, highlighting a significant gap for future development. Recent advances in mental health science impose additional requirements for adaptability. Clinical theory is shifting from categorical diagnoses toward dimensional and dynamic frameworks, including network-based and dynamic-systems models that conceptualize mental health states as evolving systems of interacting components (Borsboom, 2017; Scheffer et al., 2024; Ong et al., 2025). AI support must therefore remain adaptable to evolving constructs and evidence, as theoretical advances directly shape evaluation targets, risk assessment, and patient safety.

AI for mental health. The taxonomy proposed here links the tool type to appropriate evaluation requirements, guiding clinically aligned assessment. It provides a framework for tailoring evaluation to a tool’s intended function, potential risks, and stage of development, supporting research across both clinical and AI-focused venues. Its practical impact depends on integration into research practices, including evaluation reporting and comparison across studies. As mental health science increasingly adopts dimensional, network-based, and dynamic perspectives, the constructs and outcomes used in evaluation will necessarily evolve, reinforcing the need for adaptable and transparent evaluation frameworks. Operationalizing this taxonomy requires shared infrastructure, including datasets with expert annotations, standardized reporting practices, and reusable benchmarks, to move from conceptual guidance to routine evaluation use. Near-term research should prioritize longitudinal validation, safety-critical failure testing, and fairness auditing across diverse settings. The aim is not simply improved model performance, but evaluation practices that support safe, interpretable, and context-aware mental health AI.

6 Conclusion

Current evaluation practices for AI in mental health are fragmented and often misaligned with clinical, social, and user-centered needs. By adopting an interdisciplinary framework and a taxonomy of assessment-, intervention-, and information synthesis-oriented tools, responsible evaluation can ensure AI is clinically meaningful, ethically grounded, and more likely to produce real-world impact in mental health care.

Limitations

This paper proposes a taxonomy and accompanying evaluation framework for mental health AI, but several boundaries of scope should be noted. The analysis is informed by a set of published case studies, which may not fully represent the breadth of ongoing work or emerging AI for mental health tools. The taxonomy and evaluation pathways are conceptual rather than empirically validated, and their applicability may vary across clinical, cultural, and linguistic contexts. Additionally, while we outline key evaluation principles, we do not provide detailed operational metrics, leaving room for future work to refine and adapt these ideas as the field continues to develop.

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A Details about the surveyed papers

The full list of surveyed papers with the observed practices are in Tables 3–16. Psychologically grounded metrics are based on criteria derived from psychological theory, clinical research, or expert input. AI/NLP metrics, by contrast, focus on computational performance (e.g., accuracy, BLEU, ROUGE) and are largely agnostic to psychological or therapeutic soundness.

The tasks addressed in these papers are listed in Table 17.

Some papers examine mental disorders at a broad level, while others focus on specific diagnosed conditions. Among those that target specific conditions, the following named disorders are examined: *Anxiety, Depression, Suicide ideation, Cognitive distortions, Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), Bipolar Disorder, Schizophrenia, Self-harm, Anorexia, Trauma, Stress, Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (OCD), Panic, and Addiction.*

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
Linguistic Complexity Loss in Text-Based Therapy (Wei et al., 2021)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Depression Detection in Clinical Interviews with LLM-Empowered Structural Element Graph (Chen et al., 2024b)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
An Annotated Dataset for Explainable Interpersonal Risk Factors of Mental Disturbance in Social Media Posts (Garg et al., 2023)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
Lived Experience Not Found: LLMs Struggle to Align with Experts on Addressing Adverse Drug Reactions from Psychiatric Medication Use (Chandra et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Weakly-Supervised Methods for Suicide Risk Assessment: Role of Related Domains (Yang et al., 2021)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Generating Mental Health Transcripts with SAPE (Spanish Adaptive Prompt Engineering) (Lozoya et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Suicidal Risk Detection for Military Personnel (Park et al., 2020)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
C2D2 Dataset: A Resource for the Cognitive Distortion Analysis and Its Impact on Mental Health (Wang et al., 2023a)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Taking a turn for the better: Conversation redirection throughout the course of mental-health therapy (Nguyen et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	No	No	Yes
Towards Intelligent Clinically-Informed Language Analyses of People with Bipolar Disorder and Schizophrenia (Aich et al., 2022)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes

Table 3: List of surveyed papers (*part 1 of 14*).

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
PAL: Persona-Augmented Emotional Support Conversation Generation (Cheng et al., 2023)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Towards end-2-end learning for predicting behavior codes from spoken utterances in psychotherapy conversations (Singla et al., 2020)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
Detecting Bipolar Disorder from Misdiagnosed Major Depressive Disorder with Mood-Aware Multi-Task Learning (Lee et al., 2024a)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Towards Emotional Support Dialog Systems (Liu et al., 2021)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Mental Disorder Classification via Temporal Representation of Text (Kumar et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
Discourse-Level Representations can Improve Prediction of Degree of Anxiety (Juhng et al., 2023)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Ask an Expert: Leveraging Language Models to Improve Strategic Reasoning in Goal-Oriented Dialogue Models (Zhang et al., 2023)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Empowering Psychotherapy with Large Language Models: Cognitive Distortion Detection through Diagnosis of Thought Prompting (Chen et al., 2023b)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Identifying Moments of Change from Longitudinal User Text (Tsakalidis et al., 2022)	AI/NLP metrics	Yes	No	Yes	No
Multi-Level Feedback Generation with Large Language Models for Empowering Novice Peer Counselors (Chaszczewicz et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 4: List of surveyed papers (*part 2 of 14*).

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
Using Linguistic Entrainment to Evaluate Large Language Models for Use in Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (Kian et al., 2025)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Identifying Early Maladaptive Schemas from Mental Health Question Texts (Gollapalli et al., 2023)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Understanding the Therapeutic Relationship between Counselors and Clients in Online Text-based Counseling using LLMs (Li et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Diverse Perspectives, Divergent Models: Cross-Cultural Evaluation of Depression Detection on Twitter (Abdelkadir et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
PHASE: Learning Emotional Phase-aware Representations for Suicide Ideation Detection on Social Media (Sawhney et al., 2021a)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Improving the Generalizability of Depression Detection by Leveraging Clinical Questionnaires (Nguyen et al., 2022)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
What to Fuse and How to Fuse: Exploring Emotion and Personality Fusion Strategies for Explainable Mental Disorder Detection (Zanwar et al., 2023a)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
Do Large Language Models Align with Core Mental Health Counseling Competencies? (Nguyen et al., 2025a)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Cross-Lingual Suicidal-Oriented Word Embedding toward Suicide Prevention (Lee et al., 2020)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
Understanding Client Reactions in Online Mental Health Counseling (Li et al., 2023)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes

Table 5: List of surveyed papers (*part 3 of 14*).

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
IMBUE: Improving Interpersonal Effectiveness through Simulation and Just-in-time Feedback with Human-Language Model Interaction (Lin et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
PsychoGAT: A Novel Psychological Measurement Paradigm through Interactive Fiction Games with LLM Agents (Yang et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
ALBA: Adaptive Language-Based Assessments for Mental Health (Varadarajan et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Ask the experts: sourcing a high-quality nutrition counseling dataset through Human-AI collaboration (Balloccu et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Cognitive Reframing of Negative Thoughts through Human-Language Model Interaction (Sharma et al., 2023)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
A Computational Approach to Understanding Empathy Expressed in Text-Based Mental Health Support (Sharma et al., 2020)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
A Shoulder to Cry on: Towards A Motivational Virtual Assistant for Assuaging Mental Agony (Saha et al., 2022)	AI/NLP metrics	Yes	No	No	No
Knowledge-enhanced Mixed-initiative Dialogue System for Emotional Support Conversations (Deng et al., 2023)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	No	No	Yes
Language and Mental Health: Measures of Emotion Dynamics from Text as Linguistic Biosocial Markers (Teodorescu et al., 2023)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
CURE: Context- and Uncertainty-Aware Mental Disorder Detection (Kang et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes

Table 6: List of surveyed papers (*part 4 of 14*).

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
Still Not Quite There! Evaluating Large Language Models for Comorbid Mental Health Diagnosis (Hengle et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
A Cognitive Stimulation Dialogue System with Multi-source Knowledge Fusion for Elders with Cognitive Impairment (Jiang et al., 2023)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	No	No	No
KMI: A Dataset of Korean Motivational Interviewing Dialogues for Psychotherapy (Kim et al., 2025a)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Combining Hierarchical VAEs with LLMs for clinically meaningful timeline summarisation in social media (Song et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
A Simple and Flexible Modeling for Mental Disorder Detection by Learning from Clinical Questionnaires (Song et al., 2023)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
On the Way to Gentle AI Counselor: Politeness Cause Elicitation and Intensity Tagging in Code-mixed Hinglish Conversations for Social Good (Priya et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
D4: a Chinese Dialogue Dataset for Depression-Diagnosis-Oriented Chat (Yao et al., 2022)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Task-Adaptive Tokenization: Enhancing Long-Form Text Generation Efficacy in Mental Health and Beyond (Liu et al., 2023)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Gendered Mental Health Stigma in Masked Language Models (Lin et al., 2022)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
LLM Questionnaire Completion for Automatic Psychiatric Assessment (Rosenman et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes

Table 7: List of surveyed papers (*part 5 of 14*).

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
Emotion Granularity from Text: An Aggregate-Level Indicator of Mental Health (Vishnubhotla et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Leveraging Open Data and Task Augmentation to Automated Behavioral Coding of Psychotherapy Conversations in Low-Resource Scenarios (Chen et al., 2022)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
CASE: Efficient Curricular Data Pre-training for Building Assistive Psychology Expert Models (Harne et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
Do Models of Mental Health Based on Social Media Data Generalize? (Harrigian et al., 2020)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
Self-Adapted Utterance Selection for Suicidal Ideation Detection in Lifeline Conversations (Wang et al., 2023b)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
Can AI Relate: Testing Large Language Model Response for Mental Health Support (Gabriel et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Suicide Ideation Detection via Social and Temporal User Representations using Hyperbolic Learning (Sawhney et al., 2021b)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
PAIR: Prompt-Aware margin Ranking for Counselor Reflection Scoring in Motivational Interviewing (Min et al., 2022)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Crisis counselor language and perceived genuine concern in crisis conversations (Buda et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Empirical Evaluation of Pre-trained Transformers for Human-Level NLP: The Role of Sample Size and Dimensionality (V Ganesan et al., 2021)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No

Table 8: List of surveyed papers (*part 6 of 14*).

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
Roleplay-doh: Enabling Domain-Experts to Create LLM-simulated Patients via Eliciting and Adhering to Principles (Louie et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Exciting Mood Changes: A Time-aware Hierarchical Transformer for Change Detection Modelling (Hills et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	Yes	No	Yes	No
SMILE: Single-turn to Multi-turn Inclusive Language Expansion via ChatGPT for Mental Health Support (Qiu et al., 2024a)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
PsyGUARD: An Automated System for Suicide Detection and Risk Assessment in Psychological Counseling (Qiu et al., 2024b)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
FedTherapist: Mental Health Monitoring with User-Generated Linguistic Expressions on Smartphones via Federated Learning (Shin et al., 2023)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Modeling Empathetic Alignment in Conversation (Yang and Jurgens, 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Towards Interpretable Mental Health Analysis with Large Language Models (Yang et al., 2023)	AI/NLP metrics	Yes	No	Yes	No
Multimodal Cognitive Reframing Therapy via Multi-hop Psychotherapeutic Reasoning (Kim et al., 2025c)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
SMHD-GER: A Large-Scale Benchmark Dataset for Automatic Mental Health Detection from Social Media in German (Zanwar et al., 2023b)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
Towards Identifying Fine-Grained Depression Symptoms from Memes (Yadav et al., 2023)	AI/NLP metrics	Yes	No	No	Yes

Table 9: List of surveyed papers (*part 7 of 14*).

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
Mapping Long-term Causalities in Psychiatric Symptomatology and Life Events from Social Media (Chen et al., 2024a)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
Symptom Identification for Interpretable Detection of Multiple Mental Disorders on Social Media (Zhang et al., 2022)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Gender and Racial Fairness in Depression Research using Social Media (Aguirre et al., 2021)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
CBT-Bench: Evaluating Large Language Models on Assisting Cognitive Behavior Therapy (Zhang et al., 2025b)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
e-THERAPIST: I suggest you to cultivate a mindset of positivity and nurture uplifting thoughts (Mishra et al., 2023a)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	No	No	No
Knowledge Planning in Large Language Models for Domain-Aligned Counseling Summarization (Srivastava et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
PATIENT- ψ : Using Large Language Models to Simulate Patients for Training Mental Health Professionals (Wang et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Deciphering Cognitive Distortions in Patient-Doctor Mental Health Conversations: A Multimodal LLM-Based Detection and Reasoning Framework (Singh et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Sequential Path Signature Networks for Personalised Longitudinal Language Modeling (Tseriotou et al., 2023)	AI/NLP metrics	Yes	No	Yes	No
DisorBERT: A Double Domain Adaptation Model for Detecting Signs of Mental Disorders in Social Media (Aragón et al., 2023)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No

Table 10: List of surveyed papers (part 8 of 14).

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
Cactus: Towards Psychological Counseling Conversations using Cognitive Behavioral Theory (Lee et al., 2024b)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Development of Conversational AI for Sleep Coaching Programme (Shim, 2021)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
Social Biases in NLP Models as Barriers for Persons with Disabilities (Hutchinson et al., 2020)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Chinese MentalBERT: Domain-Adaptive Pre-training on Social Media for Chinese Mental Health Text Analysis (Zhai et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
Micromodels for Efficient, Explainable, and Reusable Systems: A Case Study on Mental Health (Lee et al., 2021)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
HealMe: Harnessing Cognitive Reframing in Large Language Models for Psychotherapy (Xiao et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
PAL to Lend a Helping Hand: Towards Building an Emotion Adaptive Polite and Empathetic Counseling Conversational Agent (Mishra et al., 2023b)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	No	No
Predicting Treatment Outcome from Patient Texts: The Case of Internet-Based Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (Gogoulou et al., 2021)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Detection of Multiple Mental Disorders from Social Media with Two-Stream Psychiatric Experts (Chen et al., 2023a)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
When LLMs Meets Acoustic Landmarks: An Efficient Approach to Integrate Speech into Large Language Models for Depression Detection (Zhang et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No

Table 11: List of surveyed papers (part 9 of 14).

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
The Colorful Future of LLMs: Evaluating and Improving LLMs as Emotional Supporters for Queer Youth (Lissak et al., 2024)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	No	Yes	No
Decoding the Narratives: Analyzing Personal Drug Experiences Shared on Reddit (Bouzoubaa et al., 2024)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
A Fully Generative Motivational Interviewing Counsellor Chatbot for Moving Smokers Towards the Decision to Quit (Mahmood et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
PsyDial: A Large-scale Long-term Conversational Dataset for Mental Health Support (Qiu and Lan, 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
SpeechT-RAG: Reliable Depression Detection in LLMs with Retrieval-Augmented Generation Using Speech Timing Information (Zhang et al., 2025c)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
DeepWell-Adol: A Scalable Expert-Based Dialogue Corpus for Adolescent Positive Mental Health and Wellbeing Promotion (Qiu et al., 2025b)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Hanging in the Balance: Pivotal Moments in Crisis Counseling Conversations (Nguyen et al., 2025b)	Psychologically grounded metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Assess and Prompt: A Generative RL Framework for Improving Engagement in Online Mental Health Communities (Gaur et al., 2025)	AI/NLP metrics	Yes	No	No	Yes
AnnaAgent: Dynamic Evolution Agent System with Multi-Session Memory for Realistic Seeker Simulation (Wang et al., 2025a)	Psychologically grounded metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Tracking Life’s Ups and Downs: Mining Life Events from Social Media Posts for Mental Health Analysis (Lv et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes

Table 12: List of surveyed papers (*part 10 of 14*).

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
Can Large Language Models Identify Implicit Suicidal Ideation? An Empirical Evaluation (Li et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Eeyore: Realistic Depression Simulation via Expert-in-the-Loop Supervised and Preference Optimization (Liu et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Dialogue Systems for Emotional Support via Value Reinforcement (Kim et al., 2025b)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
MultiAgentESC: A LLM-based Multi-Agent Collaboration Framework for Emotional Support Conversation (Xu et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
MAGI: Multi-Agent Guided Interview for Psychiatric Assessment (Bi et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Systematic Evaluation of Auto-Encoding and Large Language Model Representations for Capturing Author States and Traits (Singh et al., 2025)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
The Pursuit of Empathy: Evaluating Small Language Models for PTSD Dialogue Support (Bn et al., 2025a)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Just a Scratch: Enhancing LLM Capabilities for Self-harm Detection through Intent Differentiation and Emoji Interpretation (Ghosh et al., 2025)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Temporal reasoning for timeline summarisation in social media (Song et al., 2025b)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
MIRROR: Multimodal Cognitive Reframing Therapy for Rolling with Resistance (Kim et al., 2025d)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 13: List of surveyed papers (*part 11 of 14*).

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
Are LLMs effective psychological assessors? Leveraging adaptive RAG for interpretable mental health screening through psychometric practice (Ravenda et al., 2025)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
ReDepress: A Cognitive Framework for Detecting Depression Relapse from Social Media (Agarwal et al., 2025)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
MentalGLM Series: Explainable LLMs for Mental Health Analysis on Chinese Social Media (Zhai et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Towards AI-Assisted Psychotherapy: Emotion-Guided Generative Interventions (Haydarov et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mitigating Interviewer Bias in Multimodal Depression Detection: An Approach with Adversarial Learning and Contextual Positional Encoding (Zhang and Poellabauer, 2025)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Explainable Depression Detection in Clinical Interviews with Personalized Retrieval-Augmented Generation (Zhang et al., 2025a)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
From Heart to Words: Generating Empathetic Responses via Integrated Figurative Language and Semantic Context Signals (Lee et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Reframe Your Life Story: Interactive Narrative Therapist and Innovative Moment Assessment with Large Language Models (Feng et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
From Conversation to Automation: Leveraging LLMs for Problem-Solving Therapy Analysis (Aghakhani et al., 2025)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
Feel the Difference? A Comparative Analysis of Emotional Arcs in Real and LLM-Generated CBT Sessions (Wang et al., 2025b)	Psychologically grounded metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes

Table 14: List of surveyed papers (*part 12 of 14*).

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
CAMI: A Counselor Agent Supporting Motivational Interviewing through State Inference and Topic Exploration (Yang et al., 2025a)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Consistent Client Simulation for Motivational Interviewing-based Counseling (Yang et al., 2025b)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Does Rationale Quality Matter? Enhancing Mental Disorder Detection via Selective Reasoning Distillation (Song et al., 2025a)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Crisp: Cognitive Restructuring of Negative Thoughts through Multi-turn Supportive Dialogues (Zhou et al., 2025a)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
ProMind-LLM: Proactive Mental Health Care via Causal Reasoning with Sensor Data (Zheng et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
EmoAgent: Assessing and Safeguarding Human-AI Interaction for Mental Health Safety (Qiu et al., 2025a)	Psychologically grounded metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
MIND: Towards Immersive Psychological Healing with Multi-Agent Inner Dialogue (Chen et al., 2025b)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
PsyDT: Using LLMs to Construct the Digital Twin of Psychological Counselor with Personalized Counseling Style for Psychological Counseling (Xie et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Third-Person Appraisal Agent: Simulating Human Emotional Reasoning in Text with Large Language Models (Hong et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	No	Yes	No
CATCH: A Novel Data Synthesis Framework for High Therapy Fidelity and Memory-Driven Planning Chain of Thought in AI Counseling (Chen et al., 2025a)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	No

Table 15: List of surveyed papers (*part 13 of 14*).

Paper	Evaluation metrics	Human evaluation	Expert evaluators	Evaluation guidelines provided	Discuss limitations of evaluation
Assessment and manipulation of latent constructs in pre-trained language models using psychometric scales (Reuben et al., 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	No	No	N. A.	No
How Real Are Synthetic Therapy Conversations? Evaluating Fidelity in Prolonged Exposure Dialogues (Bn et al., 2025b)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
KoACD: The First Korean Adolescent Dataset for Cognitive Distortion Analysis via Role-Switching Multi-LLM Negotiation (Kim and Kim, 2025)	Psychologically grounded metrics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Exploring Large Language Models for Detecting Mental Disorders (Kuzmin et al., 2025)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes
M-Help: Using Social Media Data to Detect Mental Health Help-Seeking Signals (Sathvik et al., 2025)	AI/NLP metrics	No	No	N. A.	Yes

Table 16: List of surveyed papers (*part 14 of 14*).

Application Type	Tasks
Assessment	Anxiety detection; Depression detection; Classification of interpersonal risk factors; Adverse drug reactions detection; Suicide risk detection; Cognitive distortion detection; Detection of schizophrenia disorders; Detecting bipolar disorder; Mental disorder classification; Predicting degree of anxiety; Detection of moments of change; Maladaptive schema detection; Cross-cultural evaluation of depression detection; Psychological profile generation; Measuring emotion granularity from text to detect mental health conditions; Detecting mood changes in social media users over time; Automatic detection of mental health conditions from social media posts in German; Identifying depression symptoms from memes; Multimodal LLM-based cognitive distortions detection; Personalized mood change detection from users' online text over time; Predicting treatment outcome in internet-based therapy; Classification of Reddit drug-use narratives into psychologically and socially meaningful categories; Chinese language model for psychological text analysis on social media; Evaluating how well depression detection models generalize across social media platforms; Identifying social biases toward disability in NLP models; Analyze fairness and bias in depression detection models on social media across gender and racial groups
Intervention	Emotional support conversation generation; Using entrainment in CBT; Nutrition counseling; Synthetic dialogue generation for elders with cognitive impairment; Mental illness conditioned motivational dialogue generation; Generating motivational interviewing dialogues; Cognitive reframing; AI-assisted multimodal therapy; Evaluating how well large language models can assist cognitive behavioral therapy; Developing dialogue system for mental health support; Structured, empathetic cognitive reframing in psychotherapy; LLMs as emotional supporters for queer youth; Generating synthetic therapy transcripts; Enhancing long-form text generation for psychological question-answering; Evaluating whether LLMs can provide ethical, empathetic, and theory-grounded responses for mental health support
Information synthesis	Analysis of quality of therapy conversations; Behavior code prediction; Understanding the therapeutic relationship between counselors and clients; Evaluating LLM alignment with counseling competencies; Enhancing interpersonal skills; Analysis of client reactions in online mental health counseling; Understanding empathy in mental health support text; Clinically meaningful timeline summarisation in social media; Politeness and intensity tagging in conversations; Teaching AI to automatically label behaviors in therapy conversations using small amounts of data; Scoring counselor responses for reflective listening in motivational interviewing; Creating realistic AI-simulated patients for counselor training; Counseling summarization; Patient simulation for training therapists

Table 17: Overview of the diverse tasks addressed in the surveyed papers.